

Table 1. Yield, yield attributes, N uptake, and agronomic N use efficiency of rice genotypes at different N levels. CRLRRS, Kharagpur, West Bengal, India. 1994 and 1995 WS.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N use efficiency (kg grain kg ⁻¹ N)
<i>N level (kg ha⁻¹)</i>					
0	2.1	217	2.31	45.9	-
40	3.1	235	2.56	70.2	24.0
80	3.3	247	2.70	90.7	15.1
LSD (0.05)	0.2	3.47	0.18	3.15	
<i>Genotype</i>					
IET12199	2.9	228	2.47	62.2	-
IET10664	2.9	230	2.48	67.3	-
IET8655	2.2	227	2.42	53.1	-
IET12777	2.2	222	2.27	49.5	-
IET5914	3.3	235	2.70	88.4	-
Gayatri	3.4	255	2.80	93.1	-
LSD (0.05)	0.7	13	ns	5.97	-

Table 2. Interaction effect of genotype and N application on yield, yield attributes, N uptake, and agronomic N use efficiency. CRLRRS, Kharagpur, West Bengal, India. 1994 and 1995 WS.

Variety	N level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N use efficiency (kg grain kg ⁻¹ N)
IET12199	0	2.2	212	2.31	41.4	-
	40	3.0	230	2.47	63.3	20.0
	80	3.4	242	2.64	81.8	15.0
IET10664	0	2.2	214	2.32	44.8	-
	40	3.1	232	2.48	68.5	22.0
	80	3.4	244	2.65	88.6	14.8
IET8655	0	1.5	211	2.20	35.4	-
	40	2.5	229	2.45	54.1	24.5
	80	2.6	241	2.62	69.9	13.8
IET12777	0	1.4	206	1.81	32.9	-
	40	2.5	224	2.42	50.4	28.5
	80	2.6	236	2.59	65.1	15.5
IET5914	0	2.5	218	2.56	58.8	-
	40	3.5	237	2.73	89.9	25.0
	80	3.8	249	2.82	116.3	16.3
Gayatri	0	2.7	239	2.68	61.9	-
	40	3.7	257	2.85	94.8	24.5
	80	4.0	269	2.88	122.4	15.6
LSD (0.05)						
Between genotypes		0.654	12.60	ns	5.97	
Between N levels		0.182	3.47	0.188	3.15	
Variety × N level		ns	ns	ns	7.71	

were applied at transplanting. The remaining two-thirds of the N was applied in two equal splits at maximum tillering and panicle initiation.

Grain yield and N uptake increased with each increment of N up to 80 kg ha⁻¹, which registered the maximum yield as well as N uptake (Table 1). Grain yield was observed to be closely correlated with total N uptake ($r=0.899$). Increase in grain yield occurred mainly through the contribution of number of panicles m⁻². Weight of panicle increased consistently up to 80 kg N ha⁻¹, but agronomic efficiency decreased from 24.0 to 15.1 kg grain kg⁻¹ N at 40 and 80 kg N ha⁻¹, respectively.

Genotype Gayatri recorded significantly higher yield and N uptake than other genotypes but remained on a par with genotype IET5419. Most of the IET varieties had significantly lower N uptake than the check variety because of less N content in the plant sample and also because of total dry matter production. Yield and yield components also followed similar yield responses for different genotypes. Agronomic N use efficiency was higher in IET5914 and Gayatri than in other genotypes at 80 kg ha⁻¹. The gains may be attributed to the 84% higher yield recorded over that of the control (Table 2).

For rainfed lowland rice, none of the new genotypes tested outperformed the check variety Gayatri for high N use efficiency. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Performance of Azolla hybrids in lowland rice culture

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Field experiments were conducted during the 1993 and 1994 dry seasons (June–September) to compare the effect of inoculation of *Azolla* hybrids and fertilizer N on rice yield. The experi-

ment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. The test soil was silty clay with a pH of 6.4, EC 0.45 dS m⁻¹, organic C 0.57%, 30.20 mol kg⁻¹ CEC, 320 kg available N ha⁻¹, 24.9 kg P ha⁻¹, and 273.9 kg K ha⁻¹. ADT36 rice seedlings were transplanted in 1.5-m² plots with 15- × 10-cm spacing. Superphosphate and potash as muriate of potash at 50 kg ha⁻¹ were applied as a basal dose. Nitrogen at 75 kg ha⁻¹ was applied as urea super granules (USG) alone and with *Azolla*.

USG was applied at 10 cm deep at 7 d after transplanting in between four hills of alternate rows, and prilled urea (PU) alone was applied in four split doses (40, 20, 20, and 20%) at basal, tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering stages for comparing with USG. *Azolla* hybrids AH-C1 (*A. microphylla* 4018 /*A. microphylla* 4028 (V3)), AH-C2 (*A. microphylla* 4018 /*A. microphylla* 4028 (V4)), and AH-C3 (strain of *A. microphylla* from China), and wild type *A. microphylla* (from Galapagos Islands) were

Table 1. Biomass production and nutrient content of *Azolla* hybrids.

Treatment	Biomass (t ha ⁻¹) ^a		Cumulative biomass (t ha ⁻¹)	N (%)	P (%)	K (%)
	30 DAT	50 DAT				
Control	-	-	-	-	-	-
AH-C1	7.68	1.36	9.04	4.18	0.88	1.96
AH-C2	9.86	1.96	11.82	4.95	0.90	2.10
AH-C3	7.46	1.24	8.70	3.86	0.82	1.34
<i>A. microphylla</i>	6.68	1.16	7.84	3.26	0.70	1.16
AH-C1 + USG (75 kg N ha ⁻¹)	11.98	1.92	13.90			
AH-C2 + USG (75 kg N ha ⁻¹)	12.46	2.64	15.10			
AH-C3 + USG (75 kg N ha ⁻¹)	10.64	1.74	12.38			
<i>A. microphylla</i> + USG (75 kg N ha ⁻¹)	9.68	1.62	11.30			
USG (75 kg N ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-			
PU (75 kg N ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-			
CD	3.19	0.70		0.34	0.17	0.15

^a Mean of two seasons.

Table 2. Effect of inoculation of *Azolla* hybrids and USG application on grain and straw yield of ADT36. Tamil Nadu, India.^a

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	1993 dry season	%increase over control	1994 dry season	%increase over control	1993 dry season	% increase over control	1994 dry season	% increase over control
AH-C1	6.1	44.1	5.1	42.4	7.8	58.2	6.4	41.5
AH-C2	6.6	53.8	6.1	59.9	7.5	53.3	7.5	65.9
AH-C3	5.5	28.2	5.2	36.6	6.2	26.6	6.4	18.9
<i>A. microphylla</i>	6.0	41.0	4.3	13.4	6.6	33.3	5.4	19.6
AH-C1+USG	7.4	64.1	6.2	63.4	8.1	64.4	7.8	73.2
AH-C2+USG	9.0	110.3	7.3	91.9	10.1	104.4	9.9	119.6
AH-C3+USG	6.6	53.8	5.7	51.3	7.0	42.6	6.8	51.2
<i>A. microphylla</i> + USG	7.9	84.6	5.3	39.5	8.3	68.9	6.7	48.8
USG	7.5	76.9	5.2	36.6	8.5	73.3	6.5	43.9
PU	6.3	48.7	4.5	19.1	7.2	47.1	5.6	24.6
Control	4.2	-	3.8	-	4.9	-	4.5	-
SE	1.1		0.5		1.1		0.6	
CD	2.2		1.2		2.2		1.4	

^aAv of three replications.

inoculated at 500 kg ha⁻¹ on a fresh weight basis at 10 days after transplanting. *Azolla* biomass was assessed in 1.5-m² plots 30 days after transplanting. The entire *Azolla* mass floating in each plot was harvested, the moisture drained, the net weight recorded, and biomass computed as detailed below.

After biomass was determined, *Azolla* cultures were spread uniformly in each plot under saturated conditions. Nearly 5% of the *Azolla* was left unincorporated after the first incorporation; this material was allowed to multiply up to 50 days after transplanting and then the biomass was computed. *Azolla* biomass incorporated was in the range of 9-12 t ha⁻¹ at 30 days and 2-3 t ha⁻¹ at 50 days after transplanting, depending

on the growth rate of the different *Azolla* cultures inoculated (Table 1). The cumulative *Azolla* biomass incorporated at 30 days and 50 days after transplanting was about 15 t ha⁻¹.

The USG application resulted in higher grain and straw yield than PU and the control for two consecutive dry seasons. The lower efficiency in PU treatments might be attributed to a N loss mechanism. Inoculation of *Azolla* hybrids and a wild culture of *A. microphylla* with and without fertilizer N at 75 kg N ha⁻¹ as USG resulted in significantly higher grain and straw yield in ADT36 than in the uninoculated unfertilized control (Table 2). Among the *Azolla* hybrids, incorporating *Azolla* hybrid AH-C2 with USG recorded the

largest grain and straw yield for ADT36 in both seasons compared with all other *Azolla* cultures.

These results indicate that AH-C2 has higher N₂-fixing ability and higher biomass production than other *Azolla* hybrids. Inoculation of *Azolla* hybrids coupled with USG deep placement further increased the grain and straw yield of ADT36 compared with *A. microphylla*. Results indicate that the increased N was attributed to *Azolla* hybrids as well as to the efficiency of USG. ■

Influence of sowing time on biomass production and seed yield of three green manure crops

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Sensitivity of some leguminous green manure species to photoperiod is a major constraint to increased biomass and seed production. We studied the influence of time of sowing on biomass production and seed production of three green manure crops, *Crotalaria juncea* (sunn hemp), *Phaseolus trilobus* (Pillipesara), and *Stizolobium deeringianum* (velvet bean).

Pillipesara and sunn hemp are popular green manure crops in India suited for both upland and lowland conditions. Velvet bean is a fodder legume well adapted to areas of low rainfall and poor soil fertility.

Sowing was done on the 10th of every month from Oct 1993 to Sep 1994. The experiment was conducted under irrigated upland conditions. The soil was sandy loam with pH of 7.5, EC 0.5 dS m⁻¹, 196 kg available N ha⁻¹, 17.2 kg available P ha⁻¹, and 576 kg available K ha⁻¹. The spacing was 30 × 20 cm and all crops received 21.5 kg P ha⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. The correlation between growing degree days (GDD) and